

The Writing is on the Wall: The King's Chamber Game

Proof that the Great Pyramid is not 4th Dynasty

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Abstract

There is an at times heated debate between mainstream archaeologists and historians, and alternative researchers, about the age of the monuments at Giza. Mainstream produces carbon-14 tests and ancient histories, written long after the fact, as proof, while ignoring practical difficulties with the construction. Alternative researchers propose much earlier dates. Neither side has rock-solid evidence.

Part of the problem with Giza is the total lack of inscriptions on the walls. This is contrary to typical dynastic burial practices. Luckily, Robert Bauval offers a strong clue as to what we should be looking for. There are no inscriptions in the pyramids at Giza, because writing on the walls would have obscured the actual message, which has literally been hidden in plain sight all along.

“He that hath eyes, let him see.”

There is no writing *on* the walls, because the *walls themselves are the message*. We just need to look at them in the right way, and we will see π , ϕ , e , $\sqrt{2}$, $\sqrt{3}$, $\sqrt{5}$, the Fibonacci series, and more, all spelled out in base 10 digits.

This advanced mathematical knowledge, proves that the Great Pyramid can not possibly be from the 4th Dynasty.

Keywords: Egyptology, Giza, Great Pyramid, π , ϕ , golden ratio, history of mathematics.

Best viewed and printed in colour.

Revision history:

1.0.0 * 22 May 2022 * Initial version.

1.1.0 * 23 May 2022 * Assorted bug fixes and improvements.

1.2.0 * 28 May 2022 * Bug fixes. Added 3.618. Added fractions, squares and cube roots.

Restructured and moved most diagrams to separate addendum to reduce page count.

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1. Introduction

"The language of Giza is mathematics."

Robert Bauval

"You will believe."

The architects of Giza

The King's Chamber
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Figure 1: The King's Chamber in the Great Pyramid, unfolded

As per usual, this is one of those discoveries that I stumbled onto while actually trying to find

something else.

Everyone who studies the king's chamber in the Great Pyramid marvels at the workmanship of the walls, and then promptly turns their attention to the coffer, thus missing the message all around them.

The secret they fail to see right before their eyes, was the builders recording, in beautiful rose granite, the fundamental numbers of mathematics. This is like going to an art gallery and admiring the frames instead of the masterpieces.

The process is somewhat like a game or puzzle, which I have dubbed The King's Chamber Game.

All you need to do is count blocks, an operation so simple that even a child can do it. Then we string the digits together to get our answers.

I have put all the diagrams, including those from earlier version, plus new ones, in a separate document. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6590181>

2. Nomenclature, rules and constants

For ease of reference, we abbreviate each surface as C, W, N, E, S, F, for Ceiling, West wall, North wall, East wall, South wall, and Floor.

W1 means the 1st row in the West wall, and so on. W means the west wall without the variable block, and **W** is the West wall with the variable block (see below). That block specifically is **W51** (5th row, 1st block).

The **King's Chamber Game** consists of counting blocks, with some caveats.

1. The "split" blocks on the floor are repairs and count as 1 each. Or treat them as $\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2}$ blocks. Jim Alison [1] advises,

"The floor originally had 18 blocks in six courses, although the floor presently has 21 blocks. The three blocks in the lightly shaded areas were pulled out by early explorers and have been replaced with six blocks."

I have drawn the floor in its original state, sans current repairs.

2. The suspected entrance/moveable block in SW corner is a "variable" and sometimes included, sometimes not. Jim Alison [1] again, quoting Lepre:

"In the 1970's and 80's J. P. Lepre conducted a 15 year study of the pyramids of Egypt, concentrating on the Great Pyramid. Lepre found that the southernmost block on the first course of the west wall was the one exception to the tightly fitted joints in the walls of the king's chamber. The joints around this block are 1/16th to 1/4th of an inch wide. Lepre also found that the base of this block is at the level of the floor blocks of the chamber, rather than a quarter of a cubit below the level of the floor, like all the other blocks on the first course of the walls of the chamber. Based on this information, Lepre proposed that this block may be blocking another passageway into or out of the king's chamber."

3. In one case, we exclude the narrow block in the S5 row, next to the "variable" block on west wall.

A summary of rows and surfaces. I counted the double block above the entrance as being half in each row.

Rows	West	North	East	South	Floor	Ceiling	Totals
1	1	2	1	3			7
2	4	7	5	8			24
3	4	5.5	4	6			19.5
4	5	5.5	3	9			22.5
5	4 (5)	7	5	10			26 (27)
Total	18 (19)	27	18	36	18	9	

Table 1: Summary of the blocks per row and wall

Giza frequently uses famous mathematical constants and their relatives, rounded to practical values, as follows:

Constant	Name	Value	Rounded Practical
π	Archimedes' constant	3.14159265358979...	3.14, 3.142, 3.1416
$\pi/2$		1.570796327...	1.570
e	Euler's number	2.718281828...	2.718
φ	Golden ratio	1.618033989...	1.618
φ^2	Golden ratio squared	2.618033989...	2.618
ρ	Plastic number / ratio	1.324717957...	1.3247
c	Speed of light	299,792,458	2.997924×10^8
α	Fine structure constant	≈ 0.0072973525	7.29735×10^{-3}
$\sqrt{2}$		1.414213562...	1.414
$\sqrt{3}$		1.7320508...	1.732
$\sqrt{5}$		2.236067977	2.236
$\sqrt{\pi}$		1.772453851...	1.772

Table 2: The constants and practical approximations

The diagrams in this document are created from scratch using the measurements published in *Life and Work at the Great Pyramid, Vol. II*, by C. Piazzi Smyth [2], though I mostly used the figures he included from Aiton and Ingles, rather than his own, as he did not do the top course, and admitted his figures were rather roughshod. The block sizes are not critical here, rather it is the number of blocks in each row that is important.

Rules of the King's Chamber Game

1. The game consists of counting rows of blocks.

2. Only count whole rows, except for N3 and N4, depending on the situation.
3. Do not count blocks or rows more than once in a round.
4. Generally, start at the top and work your way down.

There are three basic approaches.

1. Count along the rows.
2. Count down the walls.
3. Combine both approaches.

For the purposes of the game, the ceiling, and floor count as “a row.”

Digits in brackets are “bonus digits”. Let us begin the game.

3. The Kings Chamber Game

We start with counting along the rows, which gives us our two most important numbers, π and φ (well, φ^2 , actually).

The blocks do not give us a decimal point, so we need to add one where appropriate. The crucial thing is the sequence of digits. This is like working with a slide-rule, where the device supplies the digits, and it is up to the user to insert the decimal point at the correct location.

We begin with π .

Figure 2: The first four rows give the digits of π

A quote from physicist Richard P. Feynman, referring to the mysterious Fine Structure Constant α , says "All good theoretical physicists put this number up on their wall and worry about it."

May I suggest that modern researcher do the same with Fig. 2?

Then ϕ^2 .

Figure 3: The bottom row and floor give the digits of ϕ^2

The designers put their two most important numbers first.

That exhausts the rows, so let's start with the walls.

First is e .

Figure 4: North, east and top of south walls give the digits of e

Alternatively, with bonus digits:

Figure 5: Another way to count e

The point is that these arrangements, and the ones that follow, all work together at the same time. In particular, most of the patterns use the top few rows only. This is ingenious design. Curiously, the builders put the larger blocks at the top of the walls, rather than at the base.

To reduce the page count, I have moved most diagrams to an addendum, and I'll just show the "recipes" for other patterns here.

Another way to do e :

North 1	North 2	West 1	West 3, West 4	South 1
2.	7	1	8	3

Another way to do φ^2 :

South 1 – South 4	East
2.6	18

Or just φ :

West 1	North 1, East 1, South 1	West 2 – West 5
1.	6	18

And π , with two more digits. Start at the right edge of the top row, and then follow the blocks left, down, right, down, left, down, right.

South 1	South 2, South 3	East 3, East 4, South 4
3.	14	16

$\pi/2$:

East 1	East 2	East 3, East 4
1.	5	7

3.618 is the next number in the φ sequence... it's $\varphi^2 + 1$, or $\varphi\sqrt{5}$.

South	Floor
3.6	18

This could also be done with the East wall instead of the floor. I did it this way because when you enter the chamber, it's the vista in front of you.

The square root of 2:

Figure 6: The square root of 2

For $\sqrt{3}$, we need to exclude the narrow block next to the “variable” block at the bottom of the west wall. Although, 1.732^2 is 2.999824, and 1.733^2 is 3.003289.

Figure 7: The square root of 3

And $\sqrt{5}$:

Figure 8: The square root of 5

$\sqrt{\pi}$:

Figure 9: The square root of π

The cube roots:

$\sqrt[3]{2}$:

West 1	North 1	East 1, East 2
1.	2	6

$\sqrt[3]{3}$:

West 1	West 2	West 3	North 1
1.	4	4	2

$\sqrt[3]{5}$:

West 1	North 2	East 1
1.	7	1

Now we get to more exotic sequences, which still follow the general pattern of moving down the walls, but move between walls, and of necessity, sometimes need to backtrack a little to unused rows. We still use only whole rows.

First in the famous Fibonacci series.

The King's Chamber
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Figure 10: The famous Fibonacci sequence

Another way to do π with more digits:

South 1	South 2, South 3	East 1	East 2	Ceiling	North 1	North 2
3.	14	1	5	9	2	7

The speed of light:

North 1	East 1, East 2, South 1	Ceiling	North 2	West 3, West 4	North 7, East 4, East 5, South 4
2.	9	9	7	9	24

Another ϕ :

West 1	North 1, East 1, South 1	North 2 – North 4
1.	6	18

We also have some puzzles: patterns that spell out the digits, but the order jumps around. So they are puzzles or anagrams. First is the Fine Structure Constant, α

Figure 11: The Fine Structure Constant, α

Then π .

South 1	West 1	West 2	East 1	East 2	Ceiling	North 1	North 2
3.	1	4	1	5	9	2	7

And e :

North 1	North 2	East 1	South 2	South 1
2.	7	1	8	3

The value $e - 1$ is not used much in our mathematics, but it defines the cubit : foot ratio, and a few others. See my one-pager [The Beautiful System \[3\]](#).

West 1	North 2	East 1	South 2	South 1
1.	7	1	8	3

The plastic constant, ρ :

East 1	South 1	North 1	West 2	North 2
1.	3	2	4	7

For completeness, I've included the fractions from $\frac{1}{2}$ all the way up to $\frac{1}{11}$. This is basically a demonstration of "interesting things to do with carefully chosen multiples of 9".

$$\frac{1}{2}: C/F (9/18)$$

$$\frac{1}{3}: C/N (9/27)$$

$$\frac{1}{4}: C/S (9/36)$$

$$\frac{1}{5}: C/(N + E) (9/45)$$

$$\frac{1}{6}: C/(E + S) (9/54)$$

$$\frac{1}{7}: C/(N + S) (9/63)$$

$$\frac{1}{8}: C/(W + E + S) (9/72)$$

$$\frac{1}{9}: C/(N + E + S) (9/81)$$

$$\frac{1}{10}: C/(W + E + S + F) (9/90)$$

$$\frac{1}{11}: C/(W + N + E + S + F) (9/99)$$

The arrangement of the rows also allows us to do all the squares up to 100, by systematically adding rows, from west round to south. After 1^2 and 2^2 , the totals are cumulative.

- 1: W1
- 4: W2
- 9: W1 + W2 + W3
- 16: 9 + N2
- 25: 16 + W4 + W5
- 36: 25 + N3 + N4
- 49: 36 + N5 + E1 + E2
- 64: 49 + E3 + E4 + E5 + S1
- 81: 64 + S3 + S4
- 100: 81 + S2 + S5 + **W51**

Here's the final configuration:

Figure 12: The squares from 1 to 100

And finally, a hat tip to Robert Bauval with some Spooky Stuff. The Khafre pyramid has an affinity for 3. This is the south wall, closest to Khafre. Giza humour.

Figure 13: #333

4. Conclusion

The builders of the Giza left us a message, in some ways like the Voyager disk, telling us that they were an advanced culture with a deep love of mathematics. The evidence is rock solid, for all to see.

Giza, and the Great Pyramid in particular, is a monument to mathematics, immortalized in stone.

We could dismiss some of these patterns as creative whimsy. One can also generate numerous random strings of digits, even while keeping the “whole rows only” and “start at the top and work down” mantras. However, the first few patterns shown (π , φ^2 , e , and $\sqrt{2}$) are hard to dismiss as “co-incidence!”

If we accept the “rules of the game”, then having π , φ^2 , and e so clearly displayed, or π to several digits, should give historians and archaeologists reason to reconsider their views about Giza’s origins.

“It ain’t what you don’t know that gets you into trouble. It’s what you know for sure that just ain’t so.”

Anonymous, often attributed to Mark Twain

5. Acknowledgements

Thanks to Larry Pahl [4] and Zara Douglas for inputs and ideas.

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